
A STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND FACTOR INFLUENCING IN MARKETING

Dr. J. Jose Prabhu *¹

*¹Independent Research Associate and Visiting Professor, Department of Entrepreneurship
and Innovation, Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT

Studying consumer behavior is necessary because these mean marketers can recognize what influences consumers' purchasing choices. By comprehending how customers decide on a product they can fill in the gap in the marketplace as well as determine the items that are required and also the items that are outdated. Researching consumer actions also aids online marketers choose just how to provide their items in a way that produces optimum effect on customers. Understanding customer acquiring behaviors is the key trick to getting to as well as engaging your customers, as well as transforms them to purchase from you. The function of this paper is to combine the ideas of existing study on stature customers and also researches which examined entirely different elements of customer actions, yet coincidentally produce important factor influencing in marketing.

Keywords: Consumer behavior, Consumer marketing, Consumer decision, Consumers factors influencing, Purchase decision

I. INTRODUCTION

Laroche, M. (2010) Customer behavior is the research study of people and organizations as well as how they pick and make use of services and products. It is generally concerned with psychology, inspirations, and also behaviors.

The research of customer actions consists of:

- ✓ Just how consumers assume as well as really feel around different alternatives (brand names, products, solutions, and merchants).
- ✓ How customers reason and pick between different options.
- ✓ The actions of customers while looking into and also purchasing.
- ✓ Exactly how consumer behavior is influenced by their atmosphere (peers, society, media).
- ✓ How advertising projects can be adapted as well as enhanced to better influence the customer.

Bearden, W. O., & Netemeyer, R. G. (1999). Customer actions are the research study of customers and the procedures they make use of to pick, make use of (take in), and also deal with services and products, including consumers' psychological, mental, as well as behavioral responses. Customer actions integrate suggestions from a number of sciences consisting of psychology, biology, chemistry, and business economics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Peter, J. P., et al (1999) examined this updated text focuses on customer shopping, buying as well as consumption action topics looking at both domestic and international theory as well as examples. It is divided right into areas on advertising foundations, consumer decision making, mental and sociological impacts on consumer choice-making and also special topics relating to public law, business acquiring and carrying out the study. The principles provided have applications in the not-for-profit and also for-profit settings. A collection of appropriate situations is likewise consisted of.

Jagdish N Sheth (1985) studied about This paper attempts to show that history of consumer actions relative to the study method, substantive expertise, and also the influence of external techniques has actually been extremely intertwined with the background of advertising thought. It describes tire timeless schools, tire supervisory schools and the behavior schools of advertising and also analyzes their impact in shaping customer actions. Lastly, it attempts to anticipate the new arising trends in consumer behavior therefore of the arising flexible marketing institution of the idea.

Asiegbu, I. F., et al (2012) studied about this paper is an attempt at supplying some representations from the consumer perspective. It takes a look at the principle of customer mindsets toward the marketing efforts of companies. Moreover, the paper recognizes the trilogy of customer attitude, consisting of examples of their dimension ranges; and also how mindsets link to the actions of customers yet note that the business would have problems influencing the purchasing behaviors of their customers straight. To indirectly influence the habits of prospects, the paper, for that reason, recommends that firms should give qualified evidence of their item advantages, remedy their consumer false impressions, offer complimentary samples, involve new innovations, and bring brand-new technologies is worth specifying, establishing, and also delivering procedures. Specifically, this paper recommends that the actions of customers can be successfully transformed into solid desired behavior by modifying the tri-components of their target consumer attitudes. Understanding and application of these can enable a company to effectively design rent-yielding methods

Johnson, E. J., et al. (2007) examined this paper and objective in this phase is to review for social psycho therapists some of the interesting studies performed in customer behavior and advertising. The focus gets on research published outside the conventional mainstream of social psychology but within the mainstream of customer research and marketing, and it attends to principles, theories, as well as methods pertinent to social and also cognitive psychology To arrange this literary works, and also to offer the reader a sense of the last few decades of the field, we have actually selected to focus on 4 topics: two standing for classic areas of questions, and 2 standing for creating ones. Our "traditional" classics are topics that have been central to consumer research study for at the very least the last 50 years: decision production and also persuasion. This is not to state that they are not centers of the present study yet rather that they have a longer traditional background and more established methods. Our "new school" subjects are impact as well as implied handling, locations that have proliferated in the customer research study, paralleling patterns in social psychology.

III. IMPORTANCE OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

A customer behavior evaluation needs to disclose:

- ❖ What customers think and exactly how they really feel concerning different choices (brands, products, and so on);
- ❖ What influences consumers to select in between various options;.
- ❖ Customers' actions while researching and shopping;.
- ❖ Just how consumers' atmosphere (good friends, household, media, etc.) affects their behavior.

Kang, Y. S., & Ridgway, N. M. (1996) Consumer behaviors are typically influenced by different elements. Marketing professionals should research customer purchase patterns as well as identify customer trends. In most cases, brand names influence customer behavior just with the things they can manage; like just how IKEA appears to urge you to invest more than what you meant to each time you stroll into the store.

So what are the factors that influence consumers to state yes? There are three categories of aspects that influence customer behavior:

1. **Personal variables:** an individual's rate of interests as well as opinions that can be affected by demographics (age, gender, society, and so on).
2. **Emotional elements:** an individual's response to an advertising and marketing message will depend on their understandings and also perspectives.
3. **Social elements:** family, friends, education and learning level, social networks, revenue, they all influence customers' actions.

IV. TYPES OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

There are four main types of consumer behavior:

1. **Complicated purchasing actions**

Luna, D., & Gupta, S. F. (2001) this kind of action is experienced when consumers are getting a costly, infrequently purchased item. They are highly involved in the purchase procedure and also customers' research study prior to dedicating to invest. Think of buying a home or cars and truck; these are an instance of intricate purchasing behavior.

2. Dissonance-reducing acquiring actions

Bauer, R. A. (1960) The consumer is highly associated with the acquisition process but has difficulties identifying the distinctions between brands. 'Harshness' can take place when the consumer worries that they will regret their option.

Envision you are purchasing a lawnmower. You will select one based upon rate and comfort, however, after the acquisition, you will seek verification that you've made the best selection.

3. Regular acquiring behavior

McCort, D. J., & Malhotra, N. K. (1993) Behavioral purchases are identified by the reality that the customer has very little involvement in the item or brand category. Visualize grocery purchasing: you most likely to the store and also buy your favored type of bread. You are showing a behavioral pattern, not solid brand name loyalty.

4. Variety looking for behavior.

In this circumstance, a consumer purchases various items not because they weren't pleased with the previous one, yet because they look for the range. Like when you are trying out brand-new shower gel aromas.

V. AFFECTS OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

Many things can affect consumer behavior, but the most frequent factors influencing consumer behavior are:

1. Advertising campaigns

Zhao, H. H., et al (2014) Marketing campaigns affect acquiring choices a lot. If done right as well as on a regular basis, with the right marketing message, they can also persuade customers to transform brands or go with much more expensive alternatives. Marketing projects can also be utilized as reminders for products/services that need to be gotten on a regular basis yet are not necessarily on clients' top of mind (like insurance policy as an example). An excellent marketing message can influence impulse purchases.

2. Financial problems

Zaichkowsky, J. L., & Garkey, J. R. (1995) For expensive products particularly (like residences or autos) economic problems play a big part. A favorable economic environment is recognized to make consumers even more confident and happy to indulge in acquisitions irrespective of their personal economic liabilities. Customers choose in a longer time period for pricey acquisitions and also the acquiring procedure can be influenced by more personal elements at the exact same time.

3. Personal preferences

Kotler, P., et al (1990) Consumer behavior can likewise be influenced by personal variables, such as disapproval, concerns, precepts, and also worths. In industries like fashion or food individual points of view are particularly effective. Promotion can, naturally, aid but at the end of the day, customers' selections are considerably affected by their preferences. If you're vegan, it matters not how many burger joint ads you see, you're probably not gonna start eating meat due to that.

4. Team impact

Peer pressure likewise influences customer behavior. What our members of the family, classmates, instant loved ones, neighbors, and also acquaintances think or do can play a considerable role in our choices. Social psychology affects consumer behaviour. Selecting convenience food over home-cooked dishes, as an example, is just one of such circumstances. Education levels, as well as social aspects, can have an influence.

5. Buying power

Last but not least, our purchasing power plays a considerable duty in influencing our actions. Unless you are a billionaire, you will certainly take your budget plan into consideration prior to purchasing choice. The product may be superb, the marketing might be on factor, but if you do not have the money for it, you won't acquire it. Segmenting customers based upon their buying ability will help marketing experts identify eligible customers as well as accomplish far better results.

VI. PATTERNS OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

McFall, J. (1969) Buying behavior patterns are not identified with getting routines. Behaviors are created as tendencies towards an activity as well as they end up being spontaneous in time, while patterns reveal a predictable psychological layout. Each client has his special purchasing routines, while purchasing behaviors patterns are cumulative and also offer online marketers a one-of-a-kind characterization. Consumer behavior patterns can be organized into:

1. Area of purchase

A lot of the moment consumers will separate their purchases in a number of shops even if all items are offered in the exact same store. Think of your favorite hypermarket: although you can locate clothing as well as shoes there also, you're most likely getting those from actual garments brand names.

When a customer has the capacity and the accessibility to purchase the exact same items in different shops, they are not permanently faithful to any kind of shop, unless that's the only store they have accessibility to. Examining customer actions in regards to the option of location will certainly assist online marketers to identify vital shop areas.

2. Purchase of Products

Things to consider: the things that were purchased and how much of each product was bought. Necessity items can be acquired in bulk while deluxe products are most likely to be acquired less regularly and also in tiny amounts. The quantity of each thing purchased is influenced by the perishability of the item, the buying power of the purchaser, a device of sale, cost, number of consumers for whom the item is intended, etc. Assessing a purchasing cart can offer online marketers great deals of consumer understandings.

3. Time and frequency of purchase

Customers will certainly go shopping according to their usefulness as well as will certainly expect solutions even throughout the oddest hrs; especially currently in the period of shopping where whatever is just a couple of clicks away. It's the store's duty to meet these needs by determining an acquisition pattern and match its service according to the moment as well as the frequency of acquisitions. Something to bear in mind: seasonal variations and also regional differences needs to likewise be made up.

4. Method of purchase

A consumer can either walk into a shop and get an item right then and also there, or order online as well as pay online through credit card or on delivery. The approach of purchase can likewise cause more costs from the client (for online shopping, you might also be charged a delivery cost as an example). The way a client selects to acquire a product also says a great deal regarding the type of consumer he is.

VII. CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR SEGMENTATION

Weinstein, A. T. (1994) Just 33% of the firms that use customer division say they discover it substantially impactful. Client segmentation, types of buyers, has actually constantly been essential, now that customization, as well as consumer experience, is variables that determine an organization's success, efficient segmentation is even more vital.

Typically, the majority of marketers make use of 6 main kinds of behavior divisions.

1. Benefits looked for

A client who buys toothpaste can search for four different factors: lightening, sensitive teeth, taste, or rate.

When clients look into a product and services, their actions can reveal important insights right into which advantages, functions, values, make use of situations, or problems are one of the most vital inspiring variables influencing their acquisition choice. When a client positions a much higher worth on one or more advantages over the others, these primary benefits looked for are the specifying inspiring variables driving the acquisition choice for that customer.

2. Event or timing-based

An occasion, as well as timing-based behavioral segments, refer to both global as well as individual celebrations.

- Universal celebrations put on most of the customers or the target market. For example holidays and also seasonal occasions when consumers are more likely to ensure acquisitions.
- Recurring-personal celebrations are acquiring patterns for a private client that consistently repeat over a time period. For instance birthday celebrations, wedding anniversaries or getaways, month-to-month acquisitions, or even everyday rituals such as picking up a mug of coffee en route to work every morning.
- Rare-personal events are additionally related to private clients, however, they are extra irregular and spontaneous, as well as therefore harder to forecast. As an example participating in a buddy's wedding.

3. Usage price

Product or service use is one more typical means to segment consumers by behavior, based upon the frequency at which a client purchases from or connects with a product and services. Use behavior can be a solid anticipating indicator of loyalty or spin as well as, for that reason, lifetime worth.

4. Brand commitment status

Dedicated consumers are service's most valuable properties. They are less costly to maintain, typically have the highest lifetime worth, and also can become brand supporters. By assessing behavior information, consumers can be fractional by their level of commitment so marketing professionals can comprehend their needs and ensure they are pleasing them. Loyal clients are the ones who ought to obtain special treatment as well as opportunities such as special incentives programs to nurture as well as reinforce the client connection as well as incentivize ongoing future company.

5. Individual standing

There are various possible individual conditions you might have depending on your service. A few instances are:

- Non-users.
- Potential customers.
- Novice customers.
- Regular users.
- Defectors (ex-customers that have actually changed to a competitor).

VIII. CUSTOMER JOURNEY STAGE

De Keyser, A., et al (2015) Segmenting the target market base on customer readiness permits marketing professionals to line up communications and individualize experiences to boost conversion at every phase. Additionally, it aids them to uncover stages where clients are not advancing so they can determine the most significant challenges and chances for enhancement, even on post purchase behaviors.

Understanding consumer actions is a broad and also challenging task, yet with the ideal research study mix, you can start to obtain an in-depth understanding of your consumers as well as their motivations.

- **Gathering customer behavior data** - As the inspirations that affect customer behavior are so wide, a study mix consisting of a selection of information will certainly be one of the most durable. Some are much more inexpensive than others.
- **Customer Testimonials**-- Checking out client testimonials can highlight usual issues or wishes.

- **Q&A sites**-- These websites can provide you a concept of the inquiries as well as worries that individuals have in relation to your brand, product or service.
- **Surveys**-- On the internet studies can be quickly established with sites like Survey Monkey as well as enable you to ask specific concerns.
- **Emphasis teams**-- Bring a team of consumers together and also ask inquiries straight.
- **Keywords research**-- An essential of Search Engine Optimization, keyword study can inform you what customers want and the family member level of rate of interest. It additionally assists to reveal the language they are using.
- **Google Analytics**-- Analytics can be utilized to tell you where your traffic is originating from. The Target market tab shows geography, interests, and also a series of demographics.
- **Rival evaluation**-- This can give valuable info about consumers that are shopping in your vertical however do not buy from your brand. Review our article on the top rival evaluation devices.
- **Blog site comments**-- Comments on your blog site can be a great way of discovering any kind of inquiries your target market might have.
- **Twitter Experts**-- Twitter lately launched Experts, a 12,000 solid focus team of US & UK Twitter users.
- **Google Trends**-- Google Trends can aid you to understand if a topic is becoming essentially preferred.
- **Government data**-- Government data is readily available free of cost as well as can help you recognize a team, and numerous other sources can additionally be accessed without charge.
- **Social network**-- Millions of individuals mirror their lives on social media sites, so details that can improve a number of hairs of customer behavior can be revealed with the right devices.

Social intelligence and consumer behavior

The wisest thing social can assist with is collecting consumer understandings, discovered through social media sites research study, which can take all kinds of types.

You can ask specific concerns, or investigate customers discussing your brand name. It's additionally a great suggestion to go beyond your very own brand name and also listen to consumers discussing your item category generally.

Intent to acquire-- You can get an in-depth understanding of the effect that advertising and marketing projects have on your audience, beyond simple buzz.

Project evaluation-- Understand customer action to your campaigns or track brand associations and also psychological action around them.

Belief evaluation-- Comprehend the view regarding your brand name or item, as well as exactly how that adjustment in various demographics.

As consumer actions are about utilizing the item along with the inspirations around getting it in the first place, product evaluations and also feedback can be useful here, and also help with product growth.

Intelligent market segmentation-- As everyone has various inspirations, segmenting consumer's right into groups is essential to comprehend your customers in a nuanced means.

IX. IMPORTANCE OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND FACTORS INFLUENCING IN MARKETING

Emotional aspects

Constantinides, E. (2004) the understanding of a specific problem is distinct to every person and so is the understanding of different products. Psychological variables can be affected by the present circumstance, assumption of needs and problems, the capacity to process info as well as their specific mindset. Therefore, marketing professionals have to concentrate on how they depict their product and also what emotional impact it has on customers.

Personal elements

Personal elements are governed by a person's individual options and also choices, rate of interests, likes and disapproval. The sub-factor influencing individual aspects can be age, sex, and also individual problems.

Socio-Cultural elements

Muniady, R., et al (2014) Social influence is among the significant driving forces while making a decision. Social class, earnings, living culture, and firm as well as individual keeps; workplace, etc. can have a major result on consumer behavior. Of course, influencers and also various other viewpoint leaders have a significant duty in an individual's decision-making process as well. Various other factors consist of faith, race, and also race.

Exactly How Customer behavior Works?

To recognize just how Customer behavior functions we require understanding how Perception works.

Perception is the procedure whereby we pick, translate and also organize data to produce a rational sequence that is significant. Assumption can be depending on the stimuli we obtain, exactly how we react to those stimulations and also the conditions of our environments when we get the stimuli.

Now, every marketing expert works on maximizing their gains via assumption. This is a crucial subject of consumer behavior as the understanding of an item is the make it or damage it deal for the given product's life process.

X. THE FOUR CORNERSTONES OF UNDERSTANDING ARE

Selective attention

Kumar, A. A., & Babu, S. (2014) Careful interests are when you choose some specific inputs/stimuli and also select to disregard others in a team of stimuli. Basically, in simpler terms, not all info reaches as well as attaches to you. You perceive the details you associate with.

Discerning retention

Te'eni-Harari, T., & Hornik, J. (2010) Discerning retention is when you keep in mind the parts of the stimulations that support your personal sensations as well as ideas and neglect the inputs that do not. In much easier terms, you remember the info that attaches to you at an emotional level.

Discerning distortion

Selective distortion is when you turn inconsistent information to comply with your personal ideas and also sensations. When an ambiguous input is offered, you sometimes might flex the details as per your will certainly to suit your existing collection of values as well as ideas. Thus there are possibilities that refined advertising methods might backfire and thus most marketing approaches are much guided.

Subliminal assumption

Ward, S. (1974) the subliminal assumption is when superb messages affect you without having a straight duty in the details provided. The fundamental example is: just how deodorants use way of life marketing to unconsciously associate the fragrance to leading a better life. Subliminal perception is generally just how you unconsciously associate with a particular item as a result of a stimulus that is not directly given.

XI. CONCLUSION

Marketing psychology attempts to recognize the manner in which customers believe, feel, factor, and also make decisions. The objective of marketing is to convince people and making a computed emotional appeal can be just what you need to land a long-term client. Regardless of what you sell, there is a high probability that the industry is jammed. The objective of advertising psychology is to get a side over the competitors. It's constantly important to remember that you're handling individuals. People are psychological. Intriguing marketing chances can be located at the junction of organizational purposes and human psychology. Take the time to understand exactly how the human mind works. It can reveal opportunities to activate favorable psychological reactions in your potential consumers. If you can locate this desired crossway, your service will undoubtedly level up. According to this design, a consumer's need is aroused or

stimulated in one of a variety of methods. The researcher finds information on alternate services to his trouble, examines competitive brand names utilizing some choice guideline, picks one, makes the acquisition and after that makes use of the item as well as examines it for future purchase choices. Systematic consideration of the basic components of this version discloses that timeless avenues of actions will be disregarded by customers and changed with brand-new choices that the Web's innovation implements. The Net has the possibility to come to be a lot more than an electronic directory. Fads indicate it fundamentally altering the means all of the marketing management as well as organization method is carried out. Traditional forms of marketing interaction are being transformed upside-down; the one-to-many design of marketing communication (the foundation of the marketing sector as we know it) is being changed.

XII. REFERENCES

- [1] Peter, J. P., Olson, J. C., & Grunert, K. G. (1999). Consumer behaviour and marketing strategy (pp. 329-48). London: McGraw-hill.
- [2] Jagdish N Sheth (1985) ,"History of Consumer Behavior: a Marketing Perspective", in SV - Historical Perspective in Consumer Research: National and International Perspectives, eds. Jagdish N. Sheth and Chin Tiong Tan, Singapore : Association for Consumer Research, Pages: 5-7.
- [3] Asiegbu, I. F., Powei, D. M., & Iruka, C. H. (2012). Consumer attitude: Some reflections on its concept, trilogy, relationship with consumer behavior, and marketing implications. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(13), 38-50.
- [4] Johnson, E. J., Pham, M. T., & Johar, G. V. (2007). Consumer behavior and marketing.
- [5] Laroche, M. (2010). Advances in internet consumer behavior and marketing strategy: Introduction to the special issue.
- [6] Bearden, W. O., & Netemeyer, R. G. (1999). Handbook of marketing scales: Multi-item measures for marketing and consumer behavior research. Sage publications.
- [7] Kang, Y. S., & Ridgway, N. M. (1996). The importance of consumer market interactions as a form of social support for elderly consumers. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 15(1), 108-117.
- [8] Lichtenstein, D. R., Burton, S., & Netemeyer, R. G. (1997). An examination of deal proneness across sales promotion types: a consumer segmentation perspective. *Journal of Retailing*, 73(2), 283-297.
- [9] Luna, D., & Gupta, S. F. (2001). An integrative framework for cross-cultural consumer behavior. *International marketing review*.
- [10] Bauer, R. A. (1960). Consumer behavior as risk taking. Chicago, IL, 384-398.
- [11] McCort, D. J., & Malhotra, N. K. (1993). Culture and consumer behavior: toward an understanding of cross-cultural consumer behavior in international marketing. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 6(2), 91-127.
- [12] Zhao, H. H., Gao, Q., Wu, Y. P., Wang, Y., & Zhu, X. D. (2014). What affects green consumer behavior in China? A case study from Qingdao. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 63, 143-151.
- [13] Zaichkowsky, J. L., & Garkey, J. R. (1995). Defending your brand against imitation: consumer behavior, marketing strategies, and legal issues. Westport, CT: Quorum Books.
- [14] Kotler, P., Armstrong, G., Harker, M., & Brennan, R. (1990). *Marketing: an introduction* (Vol. 1). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [15] McFall, J. (1969). Priority patterns and consumer behavior. *Journal of Marketing*, 33(4), 50-55.
- [16] Weinstein, A. T. (1994). *Market Segmentation: Using Demographics, Psychographics and Other Niche Marketing Techniques to Predict Customer Behavior*. Probus Publishing Co..
- [17] De Keyser, A., Schepers, J., & Konuş, U. (2015). Multichannel customer segmentation: Does the after-sales channel matter? A replication and extension. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 32(4), 453-456.
- [18] Constantinides, E. (2004). Influencing the online consumer's behavior: the Web experience. *Internet research*.
- [19] Muniady, R., Al-Mamun, A., Permarupan, P. Y., & Zainol, N. R. B. (2014). Factors influencing consumer behavior: A study among university students in Malaysia. *Asian Social Science*, 10(9), 18.

- [20] Kumar, A. A., & Babu, S. (2014). Factors influencing consumer buying behavior with special reference to dairy products in Pondicherry state. *International Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Management and Technology*, 3(1), 65-73.
- [21] Ward, S. (1974). Consumer socialization. *Journal of consumer research*, 1(2), 1-14.
- [22] Te'eni-Harari, T., & Hornik, J. (2010). Factors influencing product involvement among young consumers. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*.